

Scientific End Report for Commissioned Services Project

Study ID: 2023-DATAREX

Project name: Data Management for Research in ELIXIR (DATAREX)

Duration: 24 months

Project start date: 2024-01-01

Project end date: 2025-12-31

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Context

1. What challenges did the project address?

The DATAREX Implementation Study addressed some of the challenges that were identified in the RDM Community's [white paper](#). In summary:

- *Lack of recognition of and consensus on data steward profiles:* ELIXIR Nodes and some institutions recognise the importance of professional data stewards, but there is a lack of consensus and clarity on the responsibilities, knowledge and skills required for data stewardship. Definitions of the profile of data steward are often developed locally and vary greatly.
- *Lack of overview of the ELIXIR RDM ecosystem:* The ELIXIR activities regarding the management of research data and software are scattered, e.g., across projects, and ELIXIR platforms, communities and focus groups. An overview of how to use the available RDM resources is missing, which makes their dissemination, use and application challenging.
- *Lack of an organisational framework to share and exchange RDM expertise:* There is a diversity in expertise of RDM professionals in the Nodes due to the different

contexts they come from. This presents an opportunity to learn from one another. However, an effective framework that recognises these differences is missing. Offering a more structural opportunity for sharing expertise would be highly beneficial.

- *Lack of a sustainable framework for RDM training expertise and activities:* RDM course portfolios have been built and a RDM trainer network has been formed, in close collaboration with the ELIXIR Training Platform. However, the work is not complete and course materials need updating. Identifying a clear portfolio owner and a proper framework for embedding RDM training activities in the ELIXIR structure is necessary next step.

2. What were the objectives of the project?

Research Data Management (RDM) is crucial for implementing FAIR and Open Science principles. ELIXIR Platforms, Nodes, and other structures have invested in RDM, resulting in valuable tools and resources. The RDM Community aims to bring together RDM professionals to coordinate ELIXIR's activities and develop its vision.

This project aimed to empower RDM professionals and contribute to improving RDM practices. The objectives covered creating a knowledge exchange forum, coordinating the RDM ecosystem, and focusing on RDM training and data brokering.

In more detail, the objectives included:

- Coordination of the Implementation Study (**WP1**)
- Definition of a Community framework and onboarding document (**WP1**)
- A forum for RDM experts for exchanging practices and ideas (**WP1**)
- An overview of the services available for management of research outputs (**WP2**)
- Coordinate RDM knowledge content, training and capacity building and best practices across the RDM ecosystem (**WP2**)
- Support the capacity building of ELIXIR Nodes in implementing RDM services via a knowledge handbook and maturity model for ELIXIR Nodes (**WP3**)
- Collecting requirements to facilitate flow of FAIR data from researchers to repositories via Node RDM services (**WP3**)

To achieve these goals, DATAREX facilitated knowledge sharing, developed resources for RDM service providers, coordinated RDM training and content, and made recommendations for enhancing data brokering services.

Delivery

3. Duration

Starting from 2024-01-01 for a period of 24 months.

4. What were the main activities carried out in the project?

- Organising monthly online meetings¹ (2nd Tuesday of the month 14-15 CET) and community engagement with activities and tasks (WP1)
- Managing the Community materials (on Google Drive), [website](#)² and mailing list (via the website) (WP1)
- Co-organising five face-to-face events during the Implementation Study (Bergen, Luxembourg, Bari, Tartu, Ghent), partly on previous ELIXIR Programme Budget and on Staff Exchange Budget (WP1)
- Establishing the Community framework and onboarding documentation (WP1)
- Maintaining an overview of the ELIXIR RDM services, including user journeys and best practices for ELIXIR resources such as RDMkit, FAIR Cookbook, DSW and TeSS, aligned with the Interoperability platform (WP2)
- Promoting and coordinating content creation for resources such as RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook through proactive engagement with domain experts and dedicated online and in-person contentathons (WP2)
- Coordinating the curation of FAIR and RDM-related training materials developed by Nodes via an online workshop, in-person events, user-testing exercises, and the [RDM Trainer Network](#) (WP2)
- Publishing RDM related learning paths via [TeSS](#), for both researchers and data stewards through a dedicated online contentathon and follow-up sessions (WP2)
- Sharing and formalising knowledge and experiences about deploying RDM services via a knowledge handbook and maturity model, including dedicated online and in-person contentathons (WP3)
- Collecting requirements for data brokering system from the data steward point of view (WP3)

Outcomes

5. What are the benefits of the project outcomes?

The DATAREX Implementation Study has delivered a coherent and sustainable basis for strengthening RDM across ELIXIR. Its outcomes have provided practical value for Data Stewards/Data Managers and other data professionals, Nodes and the wider research community. A key benefit is the improved coordination of the RDM ecosystem through an openly accessible overview of ELIXIR RDM services and resources^{3,4,5}, including

¹ Agendas, presentations and shared notes are available via the RDM Community Google Drive.

² See D'Anna, F., Jetten, M., Jareborg, N., & Andrabi, M. (2026). ELIXIR Deliverable Report - D1.2 Final version of the Community webpage containing all outcomes. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18195885>

³ See <https://elixir-europe.org/what-we-offer/guidelines/data-management>

⁴ See Welter, D., Pérez Sitjà, X., & Bösl, K. (2025). Research Data Management User Journeys. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14710086>

⁵ See Welter, D., & Bösl, K. (2025). ELIXIR DATAREX Deliverable Report - D2.1 Overview of ELIXIR services for management of research outputs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17948834>

updated user journeys and good practices⁶ (e.g., RDMkit, FAIR Cookbook, DSW, TeSS). This overview supports more consistent use of ELIXIR resources and enables Nodes to better guide researchers in applying FAIR, RDM and Open Sciences principles.

The project also established a structured Community framework⁷ and [onboarding documentation](#)⁸ that supports long term exchange of expertise between RDM professionals, strengthening the collective capacity of Nodes. The [knowledge handbook](#)⁹ and [maturity model](#)¹⁰ for ELIXIR Nodes provides practical guidance for developing and improving institutional RDM services, helping Nodes identify strengths, needs and actionable steps. The [ELIXIR RDM Learning Path](#)¹¹ in TeSS provides a structured training materials resource, giving visibility to RDM training from different Nodes within ELIXIR.¹² Additionally, the formulated requirements for data brokering systems¹³ offers recommendations and examples of how improved support and workflows could strengthen data deposition processes and overall data flow within ELIXIR. Finally, the assessment of how RDM training resources are currently curated¹⁴ gives a clearer understanding of the metadata gaps, usability issues and differing curation practices that affect the visibility of RDM training across ELIXIR.

The outcomes are well aligned with the original study objectives and we managed to advance key elements of the RDM ecosystem (e.g., services, resources, training, community building, knowledge exchange and the professionalisation of data stewardship) with active engagement of most ELIXIR Nodes and limited funding.

⁶ See Welter, D., & Bösl, K. (2025). ELIXIR DATAREX Deliverable Report - D2.2 End report on body of knowledge. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17949099>

⁷ See Andrabi, M., D'Anna, F., Jareborg, N., & Jetten, M. (2025, April 17). ELIXIR RDM Community framework. ELIXIR. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15235047>

⁸ Available via the ELIXIR intranet.

⁹ See Jetten, M., Mičetić, I., Pérez Sitjà, X., D'Anna, F., & Andrabi, M. (2026). ELIXIR Deliverable Report - D3.1 & D3.2 First versions (MVP) of the knowledge handbook and the maturity model for RDM services providers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18202900>

¹⁰ See Mičetić, I., Ded, V., Wilbrandt, J., Popleteeva, M., Niehues, A., Moure Fernandez, A., Bösl, K., Pilvar, D., Szitenberg, A., Leskošek, B., Licciulli, F., Jermiin, L., Fatima, N., Pérez Sitjà, X., D'Anna, F., Jareborg, N., Andrabi, M., & Jetten, M. (2026). Research Data Management Maturity Model (1.2.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18172336>. The Maturity Model itself is also made accessible via the aforementioned knowledge handbook.

¹¹ Cardona, A., Schnitzer, H., Hermoso Pulido, T., Moure Fernández, A., Jetten, M., Poterlowicz, K., Alloza, E., & Le Pera, L. (2026). End report on Published Learning Paths in TeSS. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18454311>

¹² Additionally, the Data Steward Learning Path will be published soon as well, following the procedures of the Learning Path Focus Group.

¹³ See D'Anna, F., Droesbeke, B., Nylinder, S., Kallberg, Y., Ded, V., Bösl, K., Wittig, U., Baccinelli, W., Cisneiros e Faria Lourenço, M., Marčetić, H., Åberg, E., & Jareborg, N. (2026). ELIXIR Deliverable Report - D3.3 Requirements for data brokering system. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17979335>

¹⁴ Pérez Sitjà, X., Lawson-Tovey, S., Bianchini, F., & Jetten, M. (2026). D2.3 End report on FAIR training resources. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18481270>

6. Who are the main beneficiaries of the project outcomes and why?

Primary beneficiaries

- **Data managers/stewards** and other RDM professionals in ELIXIR Nodes benefit from the coordinated service overview, knowledge handbook and maturity model. These resources provide structured guidance, shared best practices and a stronger foundation for professional development.
- **Members of the ELIXIR RDM Community** gain recognition, increased visibility of their expertise and a structured environment for exchanging knowledge and shaping the ELIXIR RDM ecosystem.
- **ELIXIR Platforms, Communities and Focus Groups** benefit from clearer coordination across the RDM ecosystem, improved user journeys and enhanced alignment between RDM services, interoperability developments and training activities.
- **ELIXIR Node leadership and national data coordinators** have access to practical resources to support the development of local RDM frameworks and onboarding documentation for RDM professionals, including the identification and formalisation of RDM competencies at Node level.

Secondary beneficiaries

- **Researchers and research institutions** benefit through improved data stewardship support. Stronger RDM services and clearer guidance is expected to lead to better data quality, more efficient workflows and greater adherence to FAIR and Open Science practices.
- **Repository operators, service providers and national infrastructure organisations** profit from smoother upstream data flows, more consistent metadata practices and a better-prepared community of data stewards supporting researchers.
- **Training and capacity building organisations** gain access to FAIR and RDM related training materials and learning paths via TeSS that can be integrated into courses and workshops.
- The broader **RDM community beyond ELIXIR** benefits from openly shared materials that can be reused or adapted in other national or disciplinary contexts.

7. Follow-up: what are the concrete actions that are recommended based on outcomes of this project?

Based on the outcomes of this project, the following concrete follow-up actions are recommended:

- First, sustain community engagement through a bottom-up approach by continuing follow-up activities from the work packages.

- This includes targeted workshops (e.g. on supporting Nodes in applying the RDM Maturity Model) and regular community-driven Data Stewardship and RDM resources content development activities.
- The DATAREX deliverables and reports provide a solid foundation for these follow-up activities.
- Maintaining momentum in and (short-term) funding for these activities is essential to keep the RDM Community active and responsive to emerging needs.
- Second, initiate a structured dialogue with ELIXIR Deposition Databases, in collaboration with the ELIXIR Data Platform, to discuss and operationalise the data brokering recommendations developed in DATAREX and explore opportunities for improving FAIR data flows.
- Third, actively promote and use the Data Stewardship Handbook and Maturity Model as practical guidance for Nodes and institutions, supporting goals such as building or strengthening local RDM communities and services.
 - This includes supporting onboarding and the professional development of Data Stewards/Data Managers.
 - To ensure continuity and quality, a long-term sustainability framework should be established, for example through an editorial board or governance model responsible for maintaining and evolving the Handbook and Model.
- Fourth, in parallel, promote and integrate user journeys into training programmes and service development activities.
 - This will help ensure that RDM guidance, tools and training remain aligned with real user needs and support coherent end to end workflows for researchers and data stewards.
- Finally, maintain and curate an up-to-date overview of ELIXIR RDM services and resources, establishing it as a reliable entry point for Nodes and external stakeholders.

8. How were the outcomes disseminated?

Publications and openly available resources

The DATAREX Implementation Study has delivered many publications and openly available resources. For links see section 5 under outcomes above.

Community and project related dissemination

- Presentations and discussions during face to face and hybrid events organised within the project
- Regular dissemination through RDM Community meetings and channels
- Contributions to related BioHackathon projects, including
 - BH2025, project 2 [Advancing the ELIXIR Maturity Model for RDM providers with Node-level implementation guidance](#)

- BH2025, project 15 [METRICS – Monitoring of key performance indicators for ELIXIR Services](#)
- BH2025, project 20 [New ELIXIR RIRs: Transparent and automated evaluation for a FAIRer future](#)
- BH2025, project 27 [Towards a more scalable, sustainable and integrated research data management ecosystem](#)
- BH2024, project 29 [ELIXIR FAIR Lesson Plan Handbook: advancing researchers' & data stewards' FAIR skills](#)

Conference and ELIXIR event dissemination

- Presentations and projects updated during the F2F/hybrid event that were part of the project. This includes the five face-to-face events (Bergen, Luxembourg, Bari, Tartu, Ghent) and various online contentathons and workshops.¹⁵
- Presentation at the ELIXIR Data Platform face-to-face meeting in Marseille, November 2025.
- Poster at ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2025:
<https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1120274.1>
- Workshop at ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2025 (see agenda, [Day 2, June 3](#), Enhancing RDM resources: Strengthening synergies and advancing FAIR data practices).
- Poster at ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2024:
<https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119854.1>
- Workshop (see agenda, [Day 2, June 11](#), Hands-On RDM with ELIXIR Groups: Crafting Short and Long-Term Strategies) at ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2024)

9. Project partners and collaborating institutions

- ELIXIR-AT, UniVie (Michael Feichtinger)
- ELIXIR-BE, VIB (Rafael Andrade Bueno, Flora D'Anna, Bert Droesbeke)
- ELIXIR-CH, SIB (Vassilios Ioannidis, Patricia Palagi, Grégoire Rossier)
- ELIXIR-CY, CING (Nestoras Karathanasis, Anastasis Oulas)
- ELIXIR-CZ, IOCB (Marek Suchánek), UPOL (Karel Berka, Dominik Martinát)
- ELIXIR-DE, FZJ (Nils-Christian Lübke, Helena Schnitzer, Daniel Wibberg), HITS (Ulrike Wittig), Leibniz FLI (Jeanne Wilbrandt)
- ELIXIR-EE, UT (Heleri Inno, Diana Pilvar)
- ELIXIR-IE, UG (Lars Jermiin), UCD (Alexander Douglass)
- ELIXIR-ES, BSC (Laura Portell-Silva, Aída Moure Fernández), CRG (Teresa D'Altri, Aldar Cabrelles Moñoz)
- ELIXIR-FI, CSC (Minna Ahokas, Siiri Fuchs)
- ELIXIR-FR, IFB (Jean-François Dufayard, Paulette Lieby, Saliha Zenboudji-Beddek)
- ELIXIR-GR, Athena RC (Thanasis Vergoulis), BSCR Fleming (Alexandros Dimopoulos)
- ELIXIR-IL, Weizmann (Dan Ben-Avraham, Amir Szitenberg)

¹⁵ Agendas, presentations and shared notes are available via the RDM Community Google Drive.

- ELIXIR-IT, UniPD (Ivan Mičetić), CNR (Flavio Licciulli)
- ELIXIR-LU, PNED/LNDS (Pinar Alper, Danielle Welter), UNILU (Vilem Ded, Marina Popleteeva, Hana Marčetić)
- ELIXIR-NL, Health-RI (Mijke Jetten, Anna Niehues, Walter Baccinelli, Carla Strubbia)
- ELIXIR-NO, UiO (Federico Bianchini), UiB (Korbinian Bösl), UiT (Espen Åberg, Nazeefa Fatima)
- ELIXIR-PT, BioData.pt (Daniel Faria, Gil Poiares-Oliveira, Miguel Cisneiros)
- ELIXIR-SE, UU (Niclas Jareborg, Elin Kronander, Stephan Nylander, Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström), SU (Yvonne Kallberg)
- ELIXIR-SI, UL (Brane Leskošek, Marko Vidak, Nadja Žlender), NIB (Marko Petek)
- ELIXIR-UK, UNIMAN (Munazah Andrabi, Nick Juty, Saskia Lawson-Tovey), UCAM (Alexia Cardona), EARLH (Xènia Pérez-Sitjà), UBRAD (Krzysztof Poterlowicz), UOXF (Allyson Lister, Susanna Sansone), UCardiff (Robert Andrews)
- EMBL-EBI (Wei Kheng Teh)